

GEMINI PROJECT LAUNCHED

EU-funded large-scale innovation action on new shared mobility services

The GEMINI Project “Greening European Mobility through cascading innovation Initiatives” has had its official kick-off meeting on 28th – 29th June in Potsdam (D).

The project will last 42 months, with a total budget of over 12 M€ and led by the Urban Electric Mobility Initiative (UEMI).

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URBAN MOBILITY DAYS

4-6 October 2023 | Seville

The GEMINI Project was present at the Urban Mobility Days (UMD), which took place in Seville, Spain, at the beginning of October. The participation in the CIVITAS Evaluation Managers’ session enriched the experience of the GEMINI partners.

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LIVING LAB KICK-OFF MEETING

Local workshop in Holte

In the Rudersdal Municipality, GEMINI partner of Greater Copenhagen organized a local workshop involving politicians, stakeholders and the mobility living lab partners. The project was presented to the local media, and the next steps within the project were defined.

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IMPACT ASSESSMENT WORKSHOP

9-10 November 2023 | Amsterdam

GEMINI partner of WP1, led by Universidad Politecnica de Madrid, has designed a survey with the aim of identifying and assessing key information regarding technological drivers and key societal goals for the design of innovative business models for shared mobility.

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SURVEY ON NEW AND SHARED MOBILITY SERVICES (NMS)

GEMINI partners of WP1, WP2 and the GEMINI MLLs, met in Amsterdam for two days of impact assessment workshop, organized by WP2 and the City of Amsterdam.

[SEE THE RESULTS](#)

GEMINI GENERAL OVERVIEW

The GEMINI project officially started 6 months ago in Potsdam. To date, guidelines have been defined and first results have been achieved. Furthermore, the presence during the Urban Mobility Days in Seville and the workshop organized in Amsterdam gave a boost to continue the work in the best direction.

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Suggested Events

GEMINI partners can register for events using the dissemination plan

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